

Module for SAMPLE ACCEPTANCE *Brucella canis*

NOTE: For samples belonging to the same owner/holder with a quantity of more than 2 units, please attach a list of the sampled animals showing the same information as in the section "SAMPLE IDENTIFICATION", and send the same list in electronic format (excel/word) to the e-mail address of the lab

DATE PRELIEVO___ ACCEPTANCE NUMBER ___

Sampling Veterinarian (to be filled by the veterinarian carrying out the sampling)

Veterinary Officer

Veterinary Practitioner

Surname and first name _____ Fiscal Code. _____

Street _____ Municipality _____ Province _____ Postal Code _____

Telephone _____ e-mail _____

Official veterinarian referent (surname and first name) _____

Competent Veterinary Unit by territory _____ Telephone _____

e-mail for sending electronic test reports _____

Data on local laboratory receiving the sample (sending to NRL)

name (seat/section) _____

Contact person (surname and first name) _____

Phone ___ e-mail for sending electronic test reports

Dog Owner/Keeper (Animal Location for NRL)

OWNER

KEEPER

Surname and first name _____ Fiscal Code. _____

Born in _____ Prov. (___) on _____ resident in _____

Street _____ Municipality _____ Province _____ Postal Code _____

Telephone _____ e-mail _____

Dog Location (only if different from that of the owner) (Sampling Location for NRL)

Street _____ Municipality _____ Province _____ Postal Code _____

Telephone reference _____ e-mail _____

Dog Provenience (additional information for NRL)

Name of Breeder / shop / kennel: _____

Street _____ Municipality _____ Province _____ Postal Code _____

Telephone reference _____ e-mail _____

SAMPLES IDENTIFICATION

Animal N.	Microchip/tattoo	Date of birth
1		

Gender M F Race ____**MATERIAL COLLECTED** Serum (minimum volume 1 ml) Blood in EDTA (minimum volume 1 ml) Urine (for males only, not less than 0.5 ml) Vaginal swabs (only for females who have recently given birth or aborted) Abortion Other (specify) _____

Animal N.	Microchip/tattoo	Date of birth
2		

Gender M F Race ____**MATERIAL COLLECTED** Serum (minimum volume 1 ml) Blood in EDTA (minimum volume 1 ml) Urine (for males only, not less than 1 ml) Vaginal swabs (only for females who have recently given birth or aborted) Abortion Other (specify) ____**PURPOSE FOR SENDING SAMPLES** Control in breeding/shop/canile infected or suspected of infection Follow-up checks on infected holdings/shops/kennels or suspected of infection Tracking as a result of positivity in breeding/shop/kennel of origin Tracking next check (specify): _____ Other (specify): _____**TESTS REQUIRED:** Antibody research for *Brucella canis* *Brucella canis* Research (isolation/PCR)

ANAMNESIS**Animal No. 1** Body temperature at sampling: ___°C

CLINICAL SYMPTOMATOLOGY:

Indicate whether the animal has undergone antibiotic treatment or other treatment during the three months prior to sampling:

TREATMENTS:

 No **YES** (specify) Start date: _____ End date: _____

Type of treatment (drugs and dosage): ____

Other information (introduction date, origin, date of breeding, delivery):

Animal No. 1 Body temperature at sampling: ___°C

CLINICAL SYMPTOMATOLOGY:

Indicate whether the animal has undergone antibiotic treatment or other treatment during the three months prior to sampling:

TREATMENTS:

 No **YES** (specify) Start date: _____ End date: _____

Type of treatment (drugs and dosage): ____

N.B. This completed form must accompany the biological material that is sent for the required investigations. Failure to provide this form or its incompleteness obliges the staff of the institute not to carry out the required examination. Cod. 1362

The Requesting Veterinarian

(Stamp and signature) I confirm that I have read the specific information published in the privacy and personal data protection section on the website www.izs.it

ANAMNESIS = KENNEL INFORMATION

QUESTION ABOUT FACILITIES	ANSWER	ADDITIONAL INFORMATION
1. Did the kennel import dogs during the last year?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	Origin of imported dog:
2. Does the facility include a maternity?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Boxes <input type="checkbox"/> Crates <input type="checkbox"/> other
3. Does the facility include separated doghouses for adults?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Boxes <input type="checkbox"/> Crates <input type="checkbox"/> common courtyard <input type="checkbox"/> Garden <input type="checkbox"/> other
4. Does the facility include recreation areas?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Boxes <input type="checkbox"/> Crates <input type="checkbox"/> common courtyard <input type="checkbox"/> Garden <input type="checkbox"/> other
5. Does the facility include a breeding area?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Boxes <input type="checkbox"/> Crates <input type="checkbox"/> common courtyard <input type="checkbox"/> Garden <input type="checkbox"/> other
6. Does the facility include a quarantine?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Boxes <input type="checkbox"/> Crates <input type="checkbox"/> common courtyard <input type="checkbox"/> Garden <input type="checkbox"/> other
7. Other activities	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Pension <input type="checkbox"/> Grooming <input type="checkbox"/> Education / agility <input type="checkbox"/> Other:

QUESTIONS ABOUT BIOSECURITY PROTOCOLS	RESPONSE	ADDITIONAL INFORMATION
1. Is a quarantine period systematically applied in case of introduction?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	Number of weeks:
2. Do sanitary protocols include regular screening for infectious diseases?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	List of screened diseases:
3. Do sanitary protocols include specific equipment for each kennel compartments?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	List of compartments:
4. Do sanitary protocols include protection equipment?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	List of protection equipments:
5. How fetuses and aborted materials are managed?	<input type="checkbox"/> internally <input type="checkbox"/> externally	<input type="checkbox"/> Incineration <input type="checkbox"/> Burying <input type="checkbox"/> Professional company <input type="checkbox"/> other
6. Usual disinfectants for cleaning doghouses	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	List of products:
7. Other comments	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	